

Brief Commentary

**Brief Commentary Based on
 Article “The Atomic Structure
 and Law as the Scientific
 Foundation of Traditional
 Chinese Medicine”**

Kunming Xu*

*College of Ocean and Earth Sciences, Xiamen University, Xiamen, Fujian
 Province 361102, China*

Traditional Chinese medical theories resemble the law and order of electronic orbitals within atoms. The principle of yin and yang interaction may be illustrated by the relationship of both 1s electrons in a helium atom; the principle of five element generation and overcoming cycles can be found in the outer electrons of a carbon atom; and eight trigrams coincide with eight electrons in a neon shell. The natural pattern is single for various parallel entities. The ancient theories in vague and general statements suffer endless doubts and disputes until we have formulated the electronic orbitals in precise mathematics to support them [1]. The breakthrough in the field of atomic structure has a great implication in Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM).

The based article has established the dimensional transformation relationships between both 1s electrons in dynamic calculus of spherical quantities (Figure 1). The rotation of one 1s electron results in another 1s electron, and rotating an electron twice results in itself after a transformation cycle. Mechanically, when you twist a strand of hemp or fiber in a fixed direction, and then let it fold back, you make a rope. A rotatory operator $\int(-\partial/\partial t)dl$ upon an electron may be regarded as a kind of twisting tension so that electronic transformations of figure 1 constitute the art of making a rope with Ω_0 and Ω_2 as two partaking strands. Both strands are intertwined together, with one strand representing yin, and the other strand yang. The helium shell provides a model for many other systems with dual elements.

***Corresponding author:** Kunming Xu, College of Ocean and Earth Sciences, Xiamen University, Xiamen, Fujian, China, Tel: +86 13666020697; E-mail: kunmingx@xmu.edu.cn

Citation: Xu K (2025) Brief Commentary Based on Article “The Atomic Structure and Law as the Scientific Foundation of Traditional Chinese Medicine”. HSOA J Altern Complement Integr Med 11: 583.

Received: April 25, 2025; **Accepted:** May 06, 2025; **Published:** May 13, 2025

Copyright: © 2025 Xu K. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Figure 1: The cyclic transformation model of both 1s electrons in a helium atom.

In a DNA molecule, both time and space strands of polynucleotide are twisted together and bonded by hydrogen bonds between nitrogenous bases, A=T and C=G. The double helix may be regarded as stepwise oscillatory LC circuits [2]. Each base pair is regarded as a capacitor, each phosphate bridge as an inductor, and each deoxyribose as an electric switch. An inductor impedes alternate current but allows direct current to pass. A capacitor cuts off direct current but allows alternating current to pass, and hydrogen bonds realize this wave connection. An electron passing through a hydrogen bond experiences two states Ω_0 and Ω_2 of 1s electrons in progression. This is a circuitry and chemical bond interpretations of the yin and yang pair (Table 1).

Scope and entity	Two strands		Interaction or specialization
	Space	Time	
General sense	Space	Time	Two symmetric dimensions
Light	Electric field	Magnetic Field	Electromagnetic wave
Helium shell	Ω_2	Ω_0	Circular functions in rotatory operation
DNA	A	T	Hydrogen bonds between nitrogenous bases capacitor
	G	C	
Zygote	Ovum	Sperm	Fertilization
Body	Yin	Yang	Ventral versus dorsal aspects
Family	Wife	Husband	Marriage and sex
Life	Plant	Animal	Photosynthesis versus Aerobic respiration
Biosphere	Abiotic	Biotic	Disorder process versus order process

Table 1: The yin and yang rope structure in life phenomena.

If the genetic substance is a rope, then one may expect that the organism encoded by the gene is a rope too. An organism develops from a single zygote resulted from the fertilization of an ovum with a sperm. An ovum is a pure spatial sphere whereas a sperm is a temporal point in symmetry with it. They are a pair of yin and yang, like the

pair of 1s electrons. The multiplication of a zygote cell leads to the sex distinction of the individual that carries the predominating hormone for all his or her life. An organism is chiral, like a carbon atom bonded to four different substituents. We inherit yin and yang from our parents. Among other space and time denotations, the ventral and dorsal aspects of a human body also constitute yin and yang poles [3].

Sex division allows the male and female to develop in time and space respectively, maximizing human capabilities. He is driving and thinking while she is expecting and feeling. The male gonad is basic, and the female gonad is acidic. The distinction of both sexes prohibits chemical neutralization or electric current between them. Only during sexual intercourse do pulses of seminal fluid pass through the reproductive organs. Hence we may compare this sex polarity between man and woman with the electric capacitor between DNA nitrogenous bases that delivers pulsing signals. A husband and a wife play the time and space roles of the family respectively. This cultural orientation is similar to the helium shell within which both electrons form a yin and yang pair (Figure 2). Thus there is an analogous pattern of yin and yang interaction within a helium atom, a DNA molecule, a zygote, an organism, a family, etc. Yin and yang pair can be explained from the perspectives of mechanics, circuitry, chemistry, and biology along with TCM in a coherent manner. Yin and yang are two poles of a capacitor, which are complementary, orthogonal, and inductive to each other.

Figure 2: The biological bond between a man, a woman, and a zygote (fetus) through the reproductive canals (the dotted and solid lines) analogous to a typical hydrogen bond O---H-N.

As we discussed the structure of a helium or a neon atom, the electrons within the atom undergoes a complete cycle, rendering the system insulated from the environment, and hence their inert chemical property. Conversely, a carbon atom is chemically active because it has only four electrons $2s2p_x2p_y2p_z$ in the outer shell. The half full electron configuration gives it maximum capability in forming chemical bonds with the other atoms. That the carbon atom is the central backbone in most organic molecules is not by accident but by the rule. Because of its tetravalent tendency to bond with the other atoms, a carbon atom is not an insulated system. Although the principle of stable electron octet remains unchanged, the shifting of octet location from within an atom to inter-atoms in an organic molecule gives it great scalability. For example, a desktop application is self-contained, but an internet application is not. The latter is much more powerful thanks to its extrovert property. The advent of extrovert carbon atoms gives the potential of interatomic chemical bonds that make organic molecules and then biomolecules possible.

An LC oscillation circuit is an idealized electromagnetic circulation. The electric charges in the capacitor drive the electric current to

pass through the inductor. The alternate current then induces magnetic flux in the inductor, which provides it with an electromotive force in the circuit, charging the capacitor in the reverse polarity. The insulated LC oscillation continues back and forth cyclically. By contrast, a stepwise LC oscillation circuitry in a DNA molecule is an open and scalable system because its LC circuits shift their location every next cycle along the sequence due to the electric current routing property of deoxyriboses (Figure 3). Although the principle of LC oscillations remains unchanged, only the extrovert stepwise LC oscillations make it possible for DNA to become the blueprint of life. Of particular importance are the hydrogen bonds that hold the base pairs together. The mathematical expression for the relationships of 1s2s2p electronic orbitals may be adapted to characterize the electron flow through a hydrogen bond.

Figure 3: Mathematical formula of a DNA molecule along with its abbreviated chemical structure. Radian angle θ_1 complements radian angle θ_1 . Arrows indicate electron flow, contrary to electric current direction.

The communication of wave signals between each base pair is through hydrogen bonds, which are implemented by the chain rules of dynamic calculus. The wave propagates from the nitrogenous base rings to the hydrogen bond bearing oxygen and nitrogen atoms (equation 1), and then to the hydrogen bonds (equation 2):

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\frac{1}{\theta'} \cdot \dot{\theta} &= \frac{dl}{d\theta} \cdot \left(-\frac{d\theta}{dt}\right) = \int \left(-\frac{\partial \Phi_0}{\partial t}\right) dl \\
 &= \int A_2 \cos\psi dl \cdot \left(-\frac{dA_1 \cos\psi'}{dt}\right) \\
 &= A_2 \int \cos\psi d\psi \frac{dl}{d\psi} \cdot (A_1 \sin\psi' \frac{d\psi'}{dt}) \\
 &= -A_1 A_2 \left(-\frac{1}{\psi'} \psi'\right) \sin\psi \sin\psi' = \Phi_1, (1) \\
 -\frac{1}{\psi'} \cdot \dot{\psi} &= \frac{dl}{d\psi} \cdot \left(-\frac{d\psi}{dt}\right) = \int \left(-\frac{\partial \Omega_0}{\partial t}\right) dl \\
 &= \int C_2 \cos\beta dl \cdot \left(-\frac{dC_1 \cos\alpha}{dt}\right) \\
 &= \int C_2 \cos\beta d\beta \frac{dl}{d\beta} \cdot (C_1 \sin\alpha \frac{d\alpha}{dt}) \\
 &= -r\omega C_1 C_2 \sin\alpha \sin\beta = \Omega_2, (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

where Φ_0 and Φ_1 denote 2s2p electrons within the nitrogen and oxygen atoms involved in each hydrogen bond, Ω_0 and Ω_2 1s electrons passing through each adjoining proton of the hydrogen bond, and the equal signs indicate the progress of electric pulses between the base pair. The meanings of all spherical quantities here are similar to those in the based article [1]. Thus the wave signal burrows through the

base pair by differential and integral chain rules. Hydrogen bonding is a dynamic electric action that delivers messages between the two bases, helping to balance the strains in the double helix. It is the narrowest gateway in delivering alternate current between nitrogenous bases. In biological sense, a hydrogen bond is such a key connection between the nitrogenous bases that the calculus chains $-1/\psi'$ and Ψ may be regarded as the gonads of yin and yang organisms respectively in figure 2.

It is interesting to note that the formulae of electronic orbitals can be customized to describe DNA molecular wave functions. Such mathematical uniformity for diverse natural phenomena reflects the universality of the natural law. The discovery of the atomic structure and law has a great influence over the mathematical expression of a DNA molecule and beyond. If the gene can be modeled by a principle similar to the atomic structure, then the body can be modeled in the same manner. That is why the five element theory, which coincides with a carbon atom property, fits into the description of a human body in TCM.

Since it is the wave of 1s electrons that burrows through the five electronic orbitals $2s2p_x2p_y2p_z2s$ in the carbon atom, a six organ theory has been rationally suggested as an alternative to the five element theory [4], in which brain is added to the traditional five organs: lung, kidney, liver, heart and spleen. Brain best corresponds to 1s electrons in the inner spherical layer so that the six organ generation cycle would be 1s (brain) \rightarrow 2s (lung) \rightarrow 2p_x (kidney) \rightarrow 2p_y (liver) \rightarrow 2p_z (heart) \rightarrow 2s (spleen) \rightarrow 1s (brain). If you omit 1s (brain) in the series, then the cycle is composed of five elements in the usual sense.

The ancient Chinese developed the yin and yang theory, the five element theory, and eight trigrams with incredible talents through their long term experience. But these theories have not been well regarded by Western scientists until recently when we broke a new ground in quantum mechanics and found exactly the same patterns of electronic orbitals within atoms. Through meaningful comparisons, we have established the main connections between the atomic structures and TCM models theoretically. The yin and yang theory corresponds to the space and time model of a helium shell, and the five element theory corresponds to the electronic orbital model of $2s2p_x2p_y2p_z2s$ within a carbon atom, both forming the foundation of TCM. A hydrogen bond of yin and yang can be modeled by the same mathematical formulae developed for the relationships of 1s2s2p electrons, providing a sound template for the characterization of diverse biological phenomena (Table 1). Eight trigrams correspond to the electronic octet within a neon shell. When applied to the interatomic occasions, the octet paradigm allows the construction of macromolecules. The genesis of life is not without preparation of organic compounds but following the course from inorganic to organic molecules and from abiotic to biotic forms.

References

1. Xu K (2025) The atomic structure and law as the scientific foundation of traditional Chinese medicine. Proc of SPIE 13554: 135540D.
2. Xu K (2009) Stepwise oscillatory circuits of a DNA molecule. Journal of Biological Physics 35: 223-230.
3. Legge D (2014) Yin and yang surfaces: an evolutionary perspective. Journal of Acupuncture and meridian studies 7: 281-290.
4. Zhou J (2009) New understanding of the basic theory of traditional Chinese medicine. Chin J Integr Med 15: 7-12.

- Advances In Industrial Biotechnology | ISSN: 2639-5665
- Advances In Microbiology Research | ISSN: 2689-694X
- Archives Of Surgery And Surgical Education | ISSN: 2689-3126
- Archives Of Urology
- Archives Of Zoological Studies | ISSN: 2640-7779
- Current Trends Medical And Biological Engineering
- International Journal Of Case Reports And Therapeutic Studies | ISSN: 2689-310X
- Journal Of Addiction & Addictive Disorders | ISSN: 2578-7276
- Journal Of Agronomy & Agricultural Science | ISSN: 2689-8292
- Journal Of AIDS Clinical Research & STDs | ISSN: 2572-7370
- Journal Of Alcoholism Drug Abuse & Substance Dependence | ISSN: 2572-9594
- Journal Of Allergy Disorders & Therapy | ISSN: 2470-749X
- Journal Of Alternative Complementary & Integrative Medicine | ISSN: 2470-7562
- Journal Of Alzheimers & Neurodegenerative Diseases | ISSN: 2572-9608
- Journal Of Anesthesia & Clinical Care | ISSN: 2378-8879
- Journal Of Angiology & Vascular Surgery | ISSN: 2572-7397
- Journal Of Animal Research & Veterinary Science | ISSN: 2639-3751
- Journal Of Aquaculture & Fisheries | ISSN: 2576-5523
- Journal Of Atmospheric & Earth Sciences | ISSN: 2689-8780
- Journal Of Biotech Research & Biochemistry
- Journal Of Brain & Neuroscience Research
- Journal Of Cancer Biology & Treatment | ISSN: 2470-7546
- Journal Of Cardiology Study & Research | ISSN: 2640-768X
- Journal Of Cell Biology & Cell Metabolism | ISSN: 2381-1943
- Journal Of Clinical Dermatology & Therapy | ISSN: 2378-8771
- Journal Of Clinical Immunology & Immunotherapy | ISSN: 2378-8844
- Journal Of Clinical Studies & Medical Case Reports | ISSN: 2378-8801
- Journal Of Community Medicine & Public Health Care | ISSN: 2381-1978
- Journal Of Cytology & Tissue Biology | ISSN: 2378-9107
- Journal Of Dairy Research & Technology | ISSN: 2688-9315
- Journal Of Dentistry Oral Health & Cosmesis | ISSN: 2473-6783
- Journal Of Diabetes & Metabolic Disorders | ISSN: 2381-201X
- Journal Of Emergency Medicine Trauma & Surgical Care | ISSN: 2378-8798
- Journal Of Environmental Science Current Research | ISSN: 2643-5020
- Journal Of Food Science & Nutrition | ISSN: 2470-1076
- Journal Of Forensic Legal & Investigative Sciences | ISSN: 2473-733X
- Journal Of Gastroenterology & Hepatology Research | ISSN: 2574-2566
- Journal Of Genetics & Genomic Sciences | ISSN: 2574-2485
- Journal Of Gerontology & Geriatric Medicine | ISSN: 2381-8662
- Journal Of Hematology Blood Transfusion & Disorders | ISSN: 2572-2999
- Journal Of Hospice & Palliative Medical Care
- Journal Of Human Endocrinology | ISSN: 2572-9640
- Journal Of Infectious & Non Infectious Diseases | ISSN: 2381-8654
- Journal Of Internal Medicine & Primary Healthcare | ISSN: 2574-2493
- Journal Of Light & Laser Current Trends
- Journal Of Medicine Study & Research | ISSN: 2639-5657
- Journal Of Modern Chemical Sciences
- Journal Of Nanotechnology Nanomedicine & Nanobiotechnology | ISSN: 2381-2044
- Journal Of Neonatology & Clinical Pediatrics | ISSN: 2378-878X
- Journal Of Nephrology & Renal Therapy | ISSN: 2473-7313
- Journal Of Non Invasive Vascular Investigation | ISSN: 2572-7400
- Journal Of Nuclear Medicine Radiology & Radiation Therapy | ISSN: 2572-7419
- Journal Of Obesity & Weight Loss | ISSN: 2473-7372
- Journal Of Ophthalmology & Clinical Research | ISSN: 2378-8887
- Journal Of Orthopedic Research & Physiotherapy | ISSN: 2381-2052
- Journal Of Otolaryngology Head & Neck Surgery | ISSN: 2573-010X
- Journal Of Pathology Clinical & Medical Research
- Journal Of Pharmacology Pharmaceutics & Pharmacovigilance | ISSN: 2639-5649
- Journal Of Physical Medicine Rehabilitation & Disabilities | ISSN: 2381-8670
- Journal Of Plant Science Current Research | ISSN: 2639-3743
- Journal Of Practical & Professional Nursing | ISSN: 2639-5681
- Journal Of Protein Research & Bioinformatics
- Journal Of Psychiatry Depression & Anxiety | ISSN: 2573-0150
- Journal Of Pulmonary Medicine & Respiratory Research | ISSN: 2573-0177
- Journal Of Reproductive Medicine Gynaecology & Obstetrics | ISSN: 2574-2574
- Journal Of Stem Cells Research Development & Therapy | ISSN: 2381-2060
- Journal Of Surgery Current Trends & Innovations | ISSN: 2578-7284
- Journal Of Toxicology Current Research | ISSN: 2639-3735
- Journal Of Translational Science And Research
- Journal Of Vaccines Research & Vaccination | ISSN: 2573-0193
- Journal Of Virology & Antivirals
- Sports Medicine And Injury Care Journal | ISSN: 2689-8829
- Trends In Anatomy & Physiology | ISSN: 2640-7752

Submit Your Manuscript: <https://www.heraldopenaccess.us/submit-manuscript>